

HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN HIV/AIDS EDUCATION IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF PAMPANGA

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative descriptive-correlational study examined the competency of grade school teachers in delivering HIV/AIDS education within the Schools Division Office of Pampanga. A total of 167 respondents from seven school clusters participated. The study assessed teachers' demographic profiles (age, sex, position, years in service, and specialization), their competency levels across communication, organization, classroom management, and adaptability, and the extent of their use of instructional strategies. Findings revealed that teachers are mostly young, have 5–15 years of experience, nearly balanced, with a slight male majority. Most are Teacher III, college graduates, MAPEH teachers with moderate participation in trainings. Teachers are moderately competent in teaching HIV/AIDS, with strengths in respectful communication and classroom support, but with limitations in multimedia use, curriculum integration, and collaboration with health professionals. Data shows that teachers moderately utilized various strategies in teaching HIV/AIDS. Approaches like discussions, role-playing, and peer education are moderately utilized, while integrating HIV/AIDS topics into other subjects is highly utilized. However, the use of multimedia, guest speakers, and community outreach is low, suggesting limited use of external and tech-based resources. Significant correlations were found between demographic variables and both teacher competence and instructional strategy use. The study concludes that while teachers are moderately prepared, there is a clear need for an action plan to improve the competence of teachers in teaching HIV/AIDS. It recommends targeted training, increased access to multimedia and external resources, integration of HIV/AIDS topics across subjects, and support for interactive, student-centered instructional approaches.

INTRODUCTION

The virus that targets the body's immune system is known as the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). At the end of the infection process, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) develops. HIV damages white blood cells in the body, impairing immunity. This increases the risk of contracting infections, some malignancies, and diseases like tuberculosis. Blood, breast milk, semen, and vaginal secretions are among the bodily fluids from which HIV is transmitted. It cannot be spread by exchanging meals, kisses, or embraces. It can also be passed from mother to child. Antiretroviral therapy (ART) is a treatment and prevention strategy for HIV. If left untreated, HIV can develop into AIDS, frequently years later. HIV/AIDS originated to non-human primates in Central and West Africa. It is likely that the disease is transferred with infected chimpanzee blood during hunting. This transmission occurred in the early 20th century. Soon, the virus spread slowly and recognized in the 1980s. Recent studies hypothesized that HIV likely came from simian immunodeficiency viruses (SIVs) which changes to adapt to human body ((Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, 2024).

HIV/AIDS remains a global public health issue, and its prevalence characterizes the world map. It obtains immense attention for planning preventive strategies, though treatment has made great strides, and there has been vast awareness, yet the virus continues to transmit itself among the vulnerable population. Educators and learners are key players in defining the knowledge and practices on HIV/AIDS and are critical components in education and prevention. Schools are learning and socialization centers; therefore, they are significant environments for the transmission of HIV/AIDS education.

HIV/AIDS is seen as a global health concern. In 2022, there were around 39 million people living with HIV worldwide, of which 1.3 million were newly infected, according to UNAIDS. Women and girls made for over half of those living with HIV (PLHIV). In addition, a projected 630,000 people died from AIDS-related causes in 2023. The World Health Organization states that HIV can cause acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), the last stage of HIV infection, and harm or decrease immune system function (Sameen et al., 2023).

There is an emphasis on the early detection of disease as the main key for its cure and prevention. Maintaining health of individuals affected by HIV/AIDS is essential. Treatment plans need to be focused and directed towards overall health. Beyond medication, WHO promotes integrated care involving nutritional support, mental health counseling, and social services. This comprehensive care model aligns with the global vision of sustainable health and well-being for all, ensuring that individuals with HIV/AIDS live long, productive lives with dignity.

In the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3: Good Health and Wellbeing, emphasize putting an end to diseases which are all over the world. Communicable diseases such as HIV/AIDS must be taken full control so that it will not be transmitted to other people. Efforts to prevent such occurrences were targeted to be made by 2030. Moreover, reducing inequalities is also needed so that patients will receive the

same amount and quality of treatment that they badly need. Particularly, target 3.3 aims to end AIDS by 2020. This requires not only medical solutions but education, especially among young people.

In the Philippines, the first HIV infection case was documented in 1984. HIV impairs a person's immune system against many infections and some types of cancer, leading to AIDS, which is characterized by severe illnesses. The number of HIV infections in the Philippines has increased, more than doubled, within the last decade. This alarming HIV crisis in the country requires urgent actions (Estadilla & de los Reyes, 2020).

The National Capital Region (NCR), CALABARZON, Central Luzon, Central Visayas, Western Visayas, and Davao are among the areas most impacted. The daily incidence increased by 411% between 2012 and 2023. With 29% of newly confirmed HIV infections in January 2023 exhibiting clinical signs of advanced HIV illness at diagnosis, late presentation in care is still an issue. The impact on men having sex with men (MSM) is disproportionate (Gangcuangco & Eustaquio, 2023). This posed significant threat to the health of Filipinos. This calls for a more sustained and directed effort to mitigate the effects of this disease.

The nation's HIV epidemic has been addressed in several ways. Access to HIV testing and treatment was increased by the Philippine HIV and AIDS Policy Act of 2018 (Republic Act 11166). Minors aged 15 to 17 can now be screened for HIV without parental consent. The expansion of HIV screening to include community-based and self-testing has been made possible in large part by community-based groups.

In line with this, the Department of Education recognized the importance of educating the young people with matters about HIV/AIDS. In 2018, DepEd issues the DepEd Order no. 31 which emphasizes the comprehensive sexuality education. This entails the teaching and learning processes about the cognitive, emotional, physical, and social aspects of sexuality. The program is based on age and culture of the learners. These topics are well-integrated across subjects such as Physical Education and Health, Araling Panlipunan, Science, and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. Starting Grade 4, sexuality education is included in the curriculum. The topics run from introduction to sexuality rights, puberty-related changes, gender concepts, sexually transmitted infections, and responsible sexual behaviors (DepEd, 2018).

The competence of teachers to teaching about HIV/AIDS is one of the most important things to consider. It is with the collaborative effort of health professionals and people themselves will this disease be mitigated. Individual knowledge and practices will come a long way to prevent HIV/AIDS. When one is knowledgeable, he/she knows how to prevent the occurrence of the disease. Communication skills as a competence of teachers in teaching HIV/AIDS is important to be considered as this is the main tool of teachers to relay information. The skill of teachers in this aspect is their weapon to clear things regarding HIV/AIDS. Effective communication—including mobilizing, sensitizing, using community meetings, and working with parents—is essential to success, according to teachers. In addition to handling stigma and adjusting communication to local contexts,

they had to provide sensitive SRHR (sexual reproductive health & rights) information. (Chilambe et al., 2023).

The majority of teachers do not use instructional materials, and the social studies curriculum's HIV/AIDS topic was not implemented with sufficient use of the facilities. The degree to which instructors in rural and urban schools use instructional materials to deliver the HIV/AIDS curriculum's social studies content differs significantly, favoring those in urban areas. It is imperative that teachers use and have access to the necessary teaching resources and facilities in order to execute the HIV/AIDS curriculum in social studies classes (Ifere et al., 2024).

With the concepts mentioned above, the researcher identified some research gaps. There are limited studies on teachers' instructional competencies in HIV/AIDS education. While there is a profound body of knowledge targeting the necessity of a good instructional practices of teachers to deliver HIV/AIDS instruction, there are limited studies which disclose the strategies utilized by teachers. The extent of teaching strategy utilization in HIV/AIDS lessons is unknown.

More so, there are limited Philippine-based data. This may be attributed to the sensitivity of the issue which limits the exploration on this aspect. The respondents may also be afraid in participating in any related study because of the stigma attached to HIV/AIDS. This caused the limited findings documented in the Philippines.

By the end of 2024, there were an estimated 40.8 million [37.0–45.6 million] HIV-positive individuals worldwide, including 39.4 [35.7–44.0 million] adults aged 15 and over and 1.4 million [1.1–1.8 million] children aged 0–14 (WHO, 2024). According to the HIV & AIDS Surveillance of the Philippines (HARP) (2023), people aged 25–34 accounted for the majority of newly diagnosed HIV cases, followed by those aged 15–24. The epidemic primarily affects young persons, as seen by the median age of infection, which was 28 years. Furthermore, about 99% of cases among young people (15–24 years old) were contracted through sexual contact, highlighting the necessity of focused education and prevention initiatives.

Educators have a significant role in providing correct and neutral information about HIV/AIDS. It is with proper knowledge that teachers will be able to disseminate factual information that will not attract bias and stigma among students. Clearing up some misconceptions about HIV/AIDS will help the students gain better understanding of the disease. Integrating HIV-related topics to various subjects will help enhance the awareness of students. Most importantly, the competence of teachers to guide students in making decisions and recognizing risky practices is essential. Teachers must be able to promote respect for individuals with HIV/AIDS.

In order to help Filipino students finish their basic education without having to worry about their health, DepEd is dedicated to providing and defending their rights to quality education and better health. By spearheading the implementation of comprehensive sexuality education (CSE), it also acknowledges the roles and duties of the educational

system in providing students with their right to good health. CSE is intended to make sure that students are receiving thorough and pertinent knowledge that can promote gender equality and empowerment in order to successfully fulfill their needs for health and protection via education. Therefore, DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2018 (Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education) was released.

Several programs in the Philippines are adapted to instill awareness of students related to HIV/AIDS. There are various programs in the Philippines that are tailored to create awareness of students pertaining to HIV/AIDS. In 2024, the Ilocos Region registered a significant rise in HIV cases, with 458 new cases between January and August. This puts the number of cases reported in the area at 3,787 since 1984. To mitigate this, schools such as Buenlag National High School in Calasiao, Pangasinan, have organized symposiums to inform the students about HIV/AIDS prevention. The purpose of these is to eliminate myths and tell the truth about transmission and prevention (GMA, 2024).

In this study entitled: “*High School Teachers’ Competency in HIV/AIDS education in the Schools Division of Pampanga*”, the researcher aims to assess the competency of high school teachers in delivering HIV/AIDS education within the Schools Division Office of Pampanga. This objective seeks to identify key areas of strength and areas requiring improvement in teachers' knowledge, skills, and approaches to HIV/AIDS education. By employing a quantitative approach, the study endeavors to analyze the factors influencing teachers' competency and provide data-driven insights that can support the development of targeted training programs, policies, and interventions to enhance the quality of HIV/AIDS education. Furthermore, the research aims to contribute to the broader understanding of the role of teacher preparedness in addressing sensitive health topics and fostering awareness among students. By highlighting the importance of teacher competency in this field, the study aspires to aid in building a more informed and proactive educational community that can effectively respond to the challenges posed by HIV/AIDS.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of competence and teaching strategies with the end goal of crafting an action plan.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Religion;
 - 1.4 Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 Position;
 - 1.6 Years in service; and
 - 1.7 Trainings and Seminars attended on HIV/AIDS?
2. What is the level of competence of teachers in teaching HIV/AIDS

- 2.1 Communication skills;
 - 2.2 Organization Skills;
 - 2.3 Classroom Management skills;
 - 2.4 Adaptability?
3. What is the extent of practice of the teaching strategies for teachers teaching HIV/AIDS education?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the level of competence of teachers?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the extent of practice of the teaching strategies for teachers teaching HIV/AIDS education?
 6. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the level of competence and the teaching strategies on HIV/AIDS Education?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in the Schools Division Office of Pampanga comprised of 7 clusters. It is a premier ISO 9001: 2015 certified educational institution composed of 807 happy schools working collaboratively towards the holistic development of the unique Capampangan learners. In addition, this study utilized purposive sampling. This approach is frequently employed in qualitative research when traits or information are needed from the sample to meet the study's goals.

Population Sampling

To estimate statistical measures for each sub-population, researchers sample each stratum using a different probability sampling technique, such as simple random sampling or cluster sampling. When a population's traits are varied and researchers wish to make sure that each characteristic is accurately represented in the sample, they use stratified sampling. This aids in the study's validity and generalizability while also preventing research biases such as under coverage bias.

The Lynch formula (1985) was used to calculate the sample size (n) at 95% confidence level (0.05)

$$n = \frac{Nz^2(p)(1-p)}{d^2}$$

N=Population

n= desired sample size

z=standard normal deviate, set at 1.96 corresponding to 95% level of significance

p=population in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic 50%

d= degree of accuracy, usually set either 0.05, 0.025 and 0.10

In this study, teachers came from the 7 Clusters of SDO Pampanga were the respondents. For Cluster 1 it is composed of Arayat and Magalang. For Cluster 2, it is composed of Sta Rita, Guagua and Lubao. Cluster 3 is composed of Floridablanca and

Porac while Cluster 4 is consists of Sta. Ana, Mexico, and Bacolor. Cluster 5 is consists of Candaba and San Luis while Cluster 6 is composed of Sto. Tomas, Minalin, Apalit, and San simon. Lastly, Cluster 7 is composed of Macabebe and Masantol. Therefore, the study has the total number of populations of 292 and a sample size of 167.

The researcher based his instrument on the study conducted by Chory et al. (2021) titled: *Perspectives of education sector stakeholders on a teacher training module to reduce HIV/AIDS stigma in Western Kenya*. The questionnaire is composed of 3 parts; first part dwells on the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, sex, position, years in service, and major; second part focuses on the level of competence of teachers in teaching HIV/AIDS; third part focuses on teaching strategies.

Validity of the Research Instrument

To determine the validity of the content of the questionnaire, the researcher sought the proficiency of five experts which includes Education Program Supervisors in Science, MAPEH, Araling Panlipunan, Values Education who have a foundational expertise in HIV/AIDS teaching. The suggestions and comments of the experts was incorporated in the survey questionnaire prior to its distribution to the respondents. An average weighted mean of 5.00 was obtained which means that the instrument is highly valid.

Tools for Data Analysis

After the gathering of data, certain statistical treatments will be utilized to analyze and interpret the results. To answer sub-problem number one on the demographic profile of the respondents, frequency and mean of the data will be computed using the following formula:

$$\frac{f}{n} = _ * 100$$

Where:

$$\frac{f}{n} = _ * 100$$

%= percentage of the participants;
f= frequency of the participants; and n= number of participants

To answer sub-problem number two and three on level of competence and extent of utilization, weighted mean will be employed.

$$WM = \frac{\sum w f}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

w = weight
 f = frequency
 $\sum wf$ = summation of weight times frequency N = total number of respondents

Likert Scale for Level of Competence

Numerical Rating	Statistical Rating	Descriptive Equivalence	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Highly Competent	The respondent is most likely to have the skills and knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS.
4	3.41-4.20	Moderately Competent	The respondent is moderately likely to have the skills and knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Slightly Competent	The respondent is not much likely to have the skills and knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Least Competent	The respondent has very limited skills and knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not Competent	The respondent has no skills and knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS.

Likert Scale for Extent of Utilization of Teaching Strategies

Numerical Rating	Statistical Rating	Descriptive Equivalence	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Highly Utilized	The respondent is most likely to utilize effective strategies for teaching HIV/AIDS.
4	3.41-4.20	Moderately Utilized	The respondent is moderately likely to utilize effective strategies for teaching HIV/AIDS.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Slightly Utilized	The respondent will not much utilize effective strategies for teaching HIV/AIDS.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Least Utilized	The respondent has very limited utilization of effective strategies for teaching HIV/AIDS.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not Utilized	The respondent never utilize effective strategies for teaching HIV/AIDS.

To answer sub-problem number four on the significant relationship between variables, Pearson r will be used. The Pearson's correlation coefficient formula is $r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$

In this formula, x is the independent variable, y is the dependent variable, n is the sample size, and \sum represents a summation of all values.

All statistical analyses will be calculated and analyzed using statistical software. Statistical decisions to reject or not to reject the null hypothesis will be determined by comparing the level of significance (α) previously set at 0.05 with the significance (p) value, where rejection is implied when $p \leq \alpha$.

Scope and Delimitation

This study determined the competence and strategies of teachers in Pampanga in teaching HIV/AIDS. Moreover, the objectives of this study include the determination of the respondents' demographic profile along age, sex, religion, highest educational attainment, position, years in service, and trainings and seminar attended on HIV/AIDS. These aspects of the demographic profile are assessed with respect to how this can affect the level of competence of teachers in terms of communication skills; organization skills; classroom management skills; and adaptability. This will also deal with extent of practice of teaching strategies of teachers. A validated survey questionnaire was the study's primary tool in eliciting answer to the objectives of the study. A quantitative study with the use of appropriate tools was employed. The study will be conducted from July to August 2025.

This study is limited to teachers teaching the subjects: (ESP/Values Education, Science, MAPEH, Araling Panlipunan in Grade 8-10. Grade 7 teachers are not included because the students do not fit in the age group. Also, the Grade 7 curriculum does not focus much on HIV/AIDS. More so, this does not include the responses of the students since the focus is the competence and strategies of teachers. This will not include other research design and instruments aside from the use of questionnaire to gather the data. Other areas of the Philippines aside from Pampanga was not included.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in frequency distribution which offers a comprehensive snapshot of the respondents' characteristics, shedding light on their age, gender, professional roles, educational background, subject specialization, years of service, and training exposure.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution as to Demographic Profile N=167

		Frequency	%
Age	Below 25 years old	11	7
	26-35 years old	102	61
	36- 45 years old	29	17
	46-55 years old	17	10
	56 years old and above	8	5
Sex	Male	85	51
	Female	82	49
Position	Teacher I	40	24
	Teacher II	41	25
	Teacher III	74	44
	Master Teacher I	11	7
	Master Teacher II	1	1
Highest Educational Attainment	College Graduate	125	75
	Master's Degree Holder	38	23
	Doctorate Degree Holder	4	2
Major	Science	22	13
	Values	22	13
	Araling Panlipunan	5	3
	MAPEH	118	71
Years of Service	5 -15 years	133	80
	16-20 years	26	16
	21-25 years	3	2
	26-30 years	4	2
	>30 years	1	1
Number of Trainings	0	36	22
	1	72	43
	2	37	22
	3	20	12
	4	2	1

The demographic profile of the 167 respondents reveals a predominantly young and early-career teaching workforce. A significant majority (61.1%) fall within the 26–35 age bracket, suggesting a relatively youthful group, possibly in the early stages of their professional journey. This is supported by the years of service data, where 79.6% have between 5 to 15 years of experience. The gender distribution is nearly balanced, with males slightly outnumbering females. Most respondents hold the position of Teacher III (44.3%), indicating a concentration in mid-level teaching roles, while only a small fraction have reached Master Teacher ranks. Educational attainment is high, with nearly three-quarters being college graduates and 22.8% holding a master’s degree, though only 2.4% have pursued doctoral studies.

In terms of specialization, MAPEH (Music, Arts, PE, and Health) dominates with 70.7% of respondents, while Science and Values Education each account for 13.2%, and Araling Panlipunan trails at 3%. This suggests a strong representation from the MAPEH discipline, possibly reflecting institutional hiring trends or curriculum demands. Training participation shows moderate engagement, with 43.1% having attended one training and 22.2% attending two. However, 21.6% have not undergone any training, which may point to gaps in professional development opportunities. Overall, the data paints a picture of a relatively young, moderately experienced teaching cohort with strong representation in MAPEH and room for growth in advanced education and training.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skills

Table 2
Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skills

	Mean	DI
1. I comfortably engage in discussing HIV/AIDS-related issues with students.	4.14	MC
2. I employ simple and suitable language when describing HIV/AIDS concepts.	4.08	MC
3. I listen attentively to students' questions and concerns regarding HIV/AIDS.	3.53	MC
4. I successfully employ storytelling or actual examples to involve students in HIV/AIDS discussions.	3.67	MC
5. I invite students to ask questions and share their ideas regarding HIV/AIDS.	3.75	MC
6. I am able to describe HIV/AIDS-related issues without instilling fear or stigma.	4.16	MC
7. I employ different communication aids (e.g., videos, posters) to support HIV/AIDS education.	3.28	SC
8. I feel at ease dispelling myths and misconceptions regarding HIV/AIDS in class.	3.58	MC
9. I am able to conduct HIV/AIDS discussions that encourage critical thinking.	3.68	MC
10. I am respectful and non-judgmental in discussing HIV/AIDS issues.	3.96	MC
AWM	3.79	MC

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Highly Competent (HC), 4.20-3.41 Moderately Competent (MC), 3.40-2.61 Slightly Competent (SL), 2.60- 1.81 Least Competent (LS), 1.80-1.00 Not Competent (NC)

The data in Table 2 reveals that teachers generally perceive themselves as moderately competent in communicating HIV/AIDS-related topics, with an overall weighted mean (AWM) of Communication 65. Most indicators fall within the "Moderately Competent" (MC) range, suggesting that educators feel reasonably confident in engaging students in discussions, using appropriate language, and fostering respectful, stigma-free environments. Notably, the highest-rated item is the ability to describe HIV/AIDS issues without instilling fear or stigma (mean = 4.16), which reflects a strong awareness of the

sensitive nature of the topic and a commitment to inclusive, empathetic communication. However, the lowest-rated item—use of communication aids such as videos and posters (mean = 3.28)—falls under the "Slightly Competent" (SC) category, indicating a potential gap in the integration of multimedia tools to enhance learning.

This suggests that while verbal communication skills are relatively strong, there may be limited access to or familiarity with supplementary teaching resources that could make HIV/AIDS education more engaging and effective. Addressing this gap through targeted training or resource provision could elevate overall competence and enrich the learning experience for students.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

Table 3
Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

	Mean	DI
1. I plan structured lesson plans for the instruction of HIV/AIDS content.	3.60	MC
2. I integrate my HIV/AIDS education lessons with curriculum standards.	3.43	MC
3. I provide adequate time for HIV/AIDS discussions in my subject area.	3.63	MC
4. I plan interactive activities like role-plays or group discussions to instruct HIV/AIDS.	3.78	MC
5. I successfully sequence HIV/AIDS lessons for logical information flow.	3.61	MC
6. I employ credible sources and current materials for HIV/AIDS instruction.	3.60	MC
7. I develop interactive worksheets or assignments to reinforce HIV/AIDS knowledge.	3.60	MC
8. I work with other teachers to incorporate HIV/AIDS education into other subjects.	3.43	MC
9. I test students' knowledge of HIV/AIDS through quizzes or tests.	3.88	MC
10. I make sure my HIV/AIDS lessons cover scientific facts as well as emotional considerations.	3.92	MC
AWM	3.65	MC

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Highly Competent (HC), 4.20-3.41 Moderately Competent (MC), 3.40-2.61 Slightly Competent (SL), 2.60- 1.81 Least Competent (LS), 1.80-1.00 Not Competent (NC)

The data in Table 3 indicates that teachers possess a moderate level of competence in organizing HIV/AIDS instruction, with an overall weighted mean of 3.65. All ten indicators fall within the "Moderately Competent" (MC) range, suggesting that while educators are generally capable of planning and delivering structured HIV/AIDS lessons, there is room for enhancement. The highest-rated items—covering both scientific facts and emotional considerations (mean = 3.92) and assessing students through quizzes or

tests (mean = 3.88)—highlight strengths in content balance and evaluation. Meanwhile, slightly lower scores in curriculum integration (mean = 3.43) and cross-disciplinary collaboration (mean = 3.43) point to areas where teachers may benefit from more support or institutional alignment.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Classroom Management Skills

The data in Table 4 indicates that teachers demonstrate a moderate level of competence in managing classrooms during HIV/AIDS instruction, with an overall weighted mean of 3.65. All ten indicators fall within the "Moderately Competent" (MC) range, suggesting that educators are generally capable of fostering respectful, inclusive, and stigma-free environments.

Table 4
Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Classroom Management Skills

	Mean	DI
1. I have ground rules in place to provide respectful discussions of HIV/AIDS.	3.60	MC
2. I manage disruptive behavior well during HIV/AIDS instruction.	3.43	MC
3. I foster a stigma-free classroom culture when discussing HIV/AIDS.	3.63	MC
4. I provide opportunities for all students to feel secure and at ease sharing thoughts on HIV/AIDS discussions.	3.78	MC
5. I reinforce positively to facilitate student involvement in HIV/AIDS education.	3.61	MC
6. I resolve conflicts or disagreements that crop up during HIV/AIDS discussions.	3.60	MC
7. I employ methods to sustain students' interest and attention when discussing HIV/AIDS.	3.60	MC
8. I adjust my strategy when students are not comfortable talking about HIV/AIDS.	3.43	MC
9. I handle student HIV/AIDS-related sensitive disclosures effectively.	3.88	MC
10. I facilitate peer cooperation in HIV/AIDS learning.	3.92	MC
AWM	3.65	MC

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Highly Competent (HC), 4.20-3.41 Moderately Competent (MC), 3.40-2.61 Slightly Competent (SL), 2.60- 1.81 Least Competent (LS), 1.80-1.00 Not Competent (NC)

The highest-rated items—facilitating peer cooperation (mean = 3.92) and handling sensitive disclosures (mean = 3.88)—highlight teachers' strengths in creating emotionally safe spaces and responding empathetically to students' personal experiences. Other areas, such as establishing ground rules (mean = 3.60) and resolving conflicts (mean = 3.60), also reflect solid classroom management foundations, though slightly lower scores

in managing discomfort (mean = 3.43) and disruptive behavior (mean = 3.43) suggest opportunities for further support and training.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

The data in Table 5 shows that teachers possess a moderate level of competence in terms of adaptability when teaching HIV/AIDS, with an overall weighted mean of 3.54. All ten indicators fall within the "Moderately Competent" (MC) range, suggesting that educators are generally flexible in adjusting their instructional strategies, communication styles, and lesson pacing to meet students' diverse needs.

Table 5
Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

	Mean	DI
1. I adapt my instructional strategies according to the needs of students in HIV/AIDS instruction.	3.43	MC
2. I am willing to incorporate new teaching materials and resources for HIV/AIDS.	3.60	MC
3. I adapt my lesson plans if students need additional time to grasp HIV/AIDS subjects.	3.42	MC
4. I incorporate students' feedback to enhance my HIV/AIDS lessons.	3.56	MC
5. I adapt my communication style according to the maturity level of students.	3.92	MC
6. I am ready to attend extra training to improve my HIV/AIDS teaching capabilities.	3.43	MC
7. I integrate newer findings on HIV/AIDS in my instruction.	3.50	MC
8. I adjust my instructional approaches when observing students having difficulties with HIV/AIDS.	3.54	MC
9. I work jointly with school health professionals to enhance HIV/AIDS education.	3.48	MC
10. I adjust my instructional methods when teaching HIV/AIDS to students with varying learning capabilities.	3.51	MC
AWM	3.54	MC

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Highly Competent (HC), 4.20-3.41 Moderately Competent (MC), 3.40-2.61 Slightly Competent (SL), 2.60- 1.81 Least Competent (LS), 1.80-1.00 Not Competent (NC)

The highest-rated item—adapting communication style based on students' maturity level (mean = 3.92)—reflects a strong awareness of developmental appropriateness, while other areas such as incorporating feedback (mean = 3.56) and adjusting instruction based on observed difficulties (mean = 3.54) indicate a responsive teaching approach. However, slightly lower scores in modifying lesson plans (mean = 3.42) and collaborating with health professionals (mean = 3.48) suggest that while teachers are open to change, there may be structural or resource-related barriers to deeper adaptability.

Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

The data in Table 6 reveals that teachers moderately utilize a range of strategies in teaching HIV/AIDS, with an overall weighted mean of 3.60. Most instructional methods—such as interactive discussions (mean = 3.76), role-playing (3.75), peer education (3.68), and storytelling (3.54)—fall within the "Moderately Utilized" (MU) category, indicating that educators are actively engaging students through participatory and student-centered approaches. The highest-rated strategy is integration with other subjects (mean = 4.22), which is classified as "Highly Utilized" (HU), suggesting that teachers are effectively embedding HIV/AIDS education across the curriculum. However, strategies like multimedia integration (mean = 3.17), expert guest speakers (3.26), and community outreach (3.27) are only "Slightly Utilized" (SU), pointing to underuse of external resources and technology-enhanced learning.

Table 6
Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

	Mean	DI
1. Interactive Discussions	3.76	MU
2. Role-Playing and Scenarios	3.75	MU
3. Multimedia Integration	3.17	SU
4. Storytelling and Case Studies	3.54	MU
5. Peer Education and Group Work	3.68	MU
6. Games and Quizzes	3.65	MU
7. Expert Guest Speakers	3.26	SU
8. Community Involvement and Outreach	3.27	SU
9. Debates and Critical Thinking Activities	3.64	MU
10. Integration with Other Subjects	4.22	HU
AWM	3.60	MU

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Highly Utilized (HU), 4.20-3.41 Moderately Utilized (MU), 3.40-2.61 Slightly Utilized (SU), 2.60- 1.81 Least Utilized (LU), 1.80-1.00 Not Utilized (NU)

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skills

Table 7
Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skill

		Age	Sex	Position	Highest Educational Attainment	Major	Years in Service	Number of Trainings
1. I comfortably engage in discussing HIV/AIDS-related issues with students.	Pearson r	.192*	0.067	-0.073	0.110	-.181*	0.117	-0.105
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.013	0.387	0.351	0.156	0.019	0.134	0.176

2. I employ simple and suitable language when describing HIV/AIDS concepts.	Pearson Correlation	-.194*	-0.038	-0.022	-0.129	-0.037	-0.045	-0.065
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.012	0.628	0.779	0.097	0.633	0.561	0.401
3. I listen attentively to students' questions and concerns regarding HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	.199**	-0.017	-0.019	0.150	-0.109	-0.125	0.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.010	0.829	0.812	0.054	0.161	0.108	0.345
4. I successfully employ storytelling or actual examples to involve students in HIV/AIDS discussions.	Pearson Correlation	-0.081	-0.065	0.144	-0.067	0.134	-0.134	0.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.298	0.404	0.063	0.387	0.084	0.085	0.284
5. I invite students to ask questions and share their ideas regarding HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	-0.101	0.002	-0.093	-0.003	0.038	-0.016	0.116
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.195	0.978	0.231	0.973	0.623	0.833	0.137
6. I am able to describe HIV/AIDS-related issues without instilling fear or stigma.	Pearson Correlation	.155*	0.137	-0.061	0.041	-0.048	0.019	-0.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.046	0.079	0.436	0.599	0.542	0.812	0.228
7. I employ different communication aids (e.g., videos, posters) to support HIV/AIDS education.	Pearson Correlation	0.047	-0.094	0.053	0.029	0.094	-.156*	0.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.550	0.226	0.497	0.714	0.226	0.045	0.085
8. I feel at ease dispelling myths and misconceptions regarding HIV/AIDS in class.	Pearson Correlation	.285**	0.007	0.047	.165*	-0.124	-0.149	0.007
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.930	0.550	0.033	0.109	0.055	0.932
9. I am able to conduct HIV/AIDS discussions that encourage critical thinking.	Pearson Correlation	.157*	-0.044	0.104	0.119	-0.076	-0.124	0.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.043	0.572	0.181	0.124	0.328	0.111	0.668
10. I am respectful and non-judgmental in discussing HIV/AIDS issues.	Pearson Correlation	-0.076	-0.104	0.029	-0.067	0.046	-0.016	0.006
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.330	0.183	0.714	0.391	0.558	0.835	0.938

The correlational analysis in Table 7 reveals statistically significant relationships between certain demographic variables and educators' competence in HIV/AIDS as to communication skills, based on a Pearson correlation at the 0.05 level of significance.

Correlational Analysis Between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

Table 8 presents the correlational analysis between demographic profile and level of competence in teaching HIV/AIDS as to organization skills using Pearson r Correlation

Table 8
Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

		Age	Sex	Position	Highest Educational Attainment	Major	Years in Service	Number of Trainings
1. I plan structured lesson plans for the instruction of HIV/AIDS content.	Pearson Correlation	.212**	-0.013	-0.008	0.113	0.026	-0.043	0.108
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.006	0.868	0.918	0.146	0.739	0.579	0.165
2. I integrate my HIV/AIDS education lessons with curriculum standards.	Pearson Correlation	0.131	0.041	-0.032	0.080	-0.107	-.163*	.228**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.092	0.598	0.684	0.307	0.167	0.035	0.003
3. I provide adequate time for HIV/AIDS discussions in my subject area.	Pearson Correlation	-.172*	-0.001	-0.054	-0.048	-0.079	-0.066	0.021
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.026	0.991	0.485	0.539	0.312	0.394	0.789
4. I plan interactive activities like role-plays or group discussions to instruct HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	0.085	0.051	0.119	0.075	0.094	0.137	-.165*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.272	0.514	0.125	0.334	0.227	0.078	0.033
5. I successfully sequence HIV/AIDS lessons for logical information flow.	Pearson Correlation	.273**	-0.085	0.022	.317**	0.019	-0.035	0.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.276	0.780	0.000	0.809	0.657	0.121
6. I employ credible sources and current materials for HIV/AIDS instruction.	Pearson Correlation	-0.032	0.068	-0.082	-0.148	0.024	-0.093	0.119
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.684	0.382	0.292	0.056	0.761	0.233	0.125
7. I develop interactive worksheets or assignments to reinforce HIV/AIDS knowledge.	Pearson Correlation	-0.105	0.014	0.014	-0.055	0.039	0.096	-0.065
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.178	0.857	0.858	0.481	0.621	0.216	0.401
8. I work with other teachers to incorporate HIV/AIDS education into other subjects.	Pearson Correlation	-0.004	0.028	-0.040	0.118	-0.087	0.128	.249**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.959	0.724	0.608	0.128	0.266	0.100	0.001

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS Classroom Management Skills

Table 9 shows the Pearson r correlation analysis examining the relationship between the demographic profile and the level of competence in teaching HIV/AIDS in terms of classroom management skills.

Table 9
Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS Classroom Management Skills

		Age	Sex	Position	Highest Educational Attainment	Major	Years in Service	Number of Trainings
1. I have ground rules in place to provide respectful discussions of HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	0.096	-0.149	-0.064	-0.042	0.092	-0.060	0.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.216	0.055	0.414	0.587	0.237	0.437	0.998
2. I manage disruptive behavior well during HIV/AIDS instruction.	Pearson Correlation	0.132	0.009	-0.140	0.049	0.116	-0.054	.237**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.089	0.907	0.072	0.528	0.134	0.488	0.002
3. I foster a stigma-free classroom culture when discussing HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	.232**	0.105	0.149	0.132	0.039	-0.149	0.003
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	0.177	0.055	0.089	0.616	0.055	0.964
4. I provide opportunities for all students to feel secure and at ease sharing thoughts on HIV/AIDS discussions.	Pearson Correlation	-.214**	0.034	0.135	-.163*	0.131	-0.002	-0.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.005	0.664	0.081	0.035	0.091	0.978	0.060
5. I reinforce positively to facilitate student involvement in HIV/AIDS education.	Pearson Correlation	-.302**	-0.070	-0.108	-0.104	0.011	.207**	0.096
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.369	0.166	0.181	0.885	0.007	0.217
6. I resolve conflicts or disagreements that crop up during HIV/AIDS discussions.	Pearson Correlation	0.145	0.010	-0.071	0.050	-0.013	-0.094	.176*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.061	0.896	0.363	0.520	0.866	0.229	0.023
7. I employ methods to sustain students' interest and attention when discussing HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	.184*	-0.016	-0.105	0.033	-0.146	-0.045	0.072
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.018	0.838	0.176	0.667	0.060	0.560	0.354
8. I adjust my strategy when students are not comfortable talking about HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	-.237**	0.006	-0.097	-.251**	-0.041	0.146	-0.016

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

Table 10
Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

		Age	Sex	Position	Highest Educational Attainment	Major	Years in Service	Number of Training
1. I adapt my instructional strategies according to the needs of students in HIV/AIDS instruction.	Pearson Correlation	-0.015	0.056	0.034	0.017	-0.046	0.058	-.189*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.849	0.470	0.662	0.826	0.553	0.457	0.015
2. I am willing to incorporate new teaching materials and resources for HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	-.196*	0.045	-0.035	-0.077	-0.126	.159*	0.056
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.011	0.562	0.655	0.322	0.104	0.040	0.472
3. I adapt my lesson plans if students need additional time to grasp HIV/AIDS subjects.	Pearson Correlation	-0.031	0.032	-0.100	-0.032	-0.110	0.008	-0.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.688	0.680	0.199	0.686	0.158	0.920	0.795
4. I incorporate students' feedback to enhance my HIV/AIDS lessons.	Pearson Correlation	0.036	0.025	0.019	-0.002	0.093	-0.120	0.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.642	0.750	0.811	0.978	0.230	0.123	0.195
5. I adapt my communication style according to the maturity level of students.	Pearson Correlation	0.057	-0.017	-0.040	-.165*	0.028	-0.043	0.035
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.461	0.827	0.608	0.033	0.718	0.584	0.651
6. I am ready to attend extra training to improve my HIV/AIDS teaching capabilities.	Pearson Correlation	.196*	-0.008	0.071	0.124	0.063	-0.132	-0.142
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.011	0.917	0.362	0.112	0.422	0.090	0.067
7. I integrate newer findings on HIV/AIDS in my instruction.	Pearson Correlation	0.088	-0.136	0.049	0.036	0.080	-0.080	0.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.258	0.079	0.529	0.645	0.302	0.307	0.085
8. I adjust my instructional approaches when observing students having difficulties with HIV/AIDS.	Pearson Correlation	-0.058	0.046	0.066	-0.035	0.039	0.043	-0.095
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.456	0.554	0.397	0.657	0.616	0.582	0.220
9. I work jointly with school health professionals to enhance HIV/AIDS education.	Pearson Correlation	-.153*	0.007	0.059	0.071	-0.023	0.113	-0.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.048	0.928	0.450	0.364	0.772	0.145	0.185
10. I adjust my instructional methods when teaching HIV/AIDS to students with varying learning capabilities.	Pearson Correlation	0.084	-0.023	-0.063	0.007	0.097	0.035	-0.057

Table 10 presents the Pearson r correlation analysis of the relationship between the demographic profile and the level of competence in teaching HIV/AIDS with respect to adaptability

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

Table 11 presents the correlational analysis between the demographic profile and extent of utilization of strategies in teaching HIV/AIDS.

Table 11
Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

		Age	Sex	Position	Highest Educational Attainment	Major	Years in Service	Number of Training
1. Interactive Discussions	Pearson Correlation	-0.015	0.056	0.034	0.017	-0.046	0.058	-.189*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.849	0.470	0.662	0.826	0.553	0.457	0.015
2. Role-Playing and Scenarios	Pearson Correlation	-.196*	0.045	-0.035	-0.077	-0.126	.159*	0.056
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.011	0.562	0.655	0.322	0.104	0.040	0.472
3. Multimedia Integration	Pearson Correlation	-0.031	0.032	-0.100	-0.032	-0.110	0.008	-0.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.688	0.680	0.199	0.686	0.158	0.920	0.795
4. Storytelling and Case Studies	Pearson Correlation	0.036	0.025	0.019	-0.002	0.093	-0.120	0.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.642	0.750	0.811	0.978	0.230	0.123	0.195
5. Peer Education and Group Work	Pearson Correlation	0.057	-0.017	-0.040	-.165*	0.028	-0.043	0.035
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.461	0.827	0.608	0.033	0.718	0.584	0.651
6. Games and Quizzes	Pearson Correlation	.196*	-0.008	0.071	0.124	0.063	-0.132	-0.142
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.011	0.917	0.362	0.112	0.422	0.090	0.067
7. Expert Guest Speakers	Pearson Correlation	0.088	-0.136	0.049	0.036	0.080	-0.080	0.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.258	0.079	0.529	0.645	0.302	0.307	0.085
8. Community Involvement and Outreach	Pearson Correlation	-0.058	0.046	0.066	-0.035	0.039	0.043	-0.095
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.456	0.554	0.397	0.657	0.616	0.582	0.220
9. Debates and Critical Thinking Activities	Pearson Correlation	-.153*	0.007	0.059	0.071	-0.023	0.113	-0.103

Action Plan to enhance the level of competence and the teaching strategies on HIV/AIDS Education

This study recommends an action plan to enhance the level of competence and the teaching strategies on HIV/AIDS education. This action plan targets the least scored items based on the conducted survey. The plan of action is divided into five aspects: Widened Use of Communication Aids (Videos, Posters, Multimedia) in HIV/AIDS instruction; Strengthened Curriculum Integration and Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration; Strengthened classroom management skills for sensitive discussions; Increased Adaptability in Lesson Planning and Collaboration with Health Professionals; and Responsive Training for Teachers based on Demographics.

Each plan of action has a corresponding objectives and strategies that will help enhance HIV/AIDS instruction. The use of materials is emphasized in the first part. Curricular adjustments were also intended to be resolved through the action plan. Managing classroom during the discussion of this sensitive topic is necessary. Lesson planning and collaboration with community professionals may also be a great help. Lastly, training teachers while considering their preferences and needs is essential in achieving the enhanced level of competence of teachers in teaching HIV/AIDS.

Table 12
Action Plan to enhance the level of competence and the teaching strategies on HIV/AIDS Education

Plan of Action	Purpose of Action	Specific Objectives	Strategies	Persons Responsible
Widened Use of Communication Aids (Videos, Posters, Multimedia) in HIV/AIDS instruction	To improve teachers' competence in using multimedia tools to enrich HIV/AIDS instruction.	Increase teachers' ability to create and use existing videos, posters, and digital materials appropriately.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct hands-on workshops on creating and using low-cost multimedia materials. Provide a repository of ready-to-use HIV/AIDS videos, infographics, and posters. Pair less tech-savvy teachers with younger, more tech-skilled colleagues (peer coaching). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Speakers Learning Facilitators Teachers

Strengthened Curriculum Integration and Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration	To align HIV/AIDS education with curriculum standards and other subject areas.	Streamline curriculum standards and integrate HIV/AIDS topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct curriculum mapping and planning on integrating HIV/AIDS topics within and across curriculum • Organize inter-department planning meetings to craft programs in support with HIV/AIDS topic enhanced curriculum. • Issue guidelines in integrating HIV/AIDS in the curriculum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School head • Curriculum Leaders • Teachers
Strengthened classroom management skills for sensitive discussions	To hone the confidence of teachers when handling student behavior during HIV/AIDS discussion	Equip teachers with strategies to manage sensitive questions and maintain respectful dialogue. Reduce classroom stigma or tension when discussing HIV/AIDS.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct training in classroom management during HIV/AIDS discussion • Provide sample Q and A scripts when questions arise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Facilitators Teachers
Increased Adaptability in Lesson Planning and Collaboration with Health	To strengthen teachers' flexibility in modifying lessons and engaging	Enable flexibility in lesson delivery Promote team teaching with the help of community professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer training on personalized lesson planning • Seek memorandum of agreement with partner agencies to ask the help of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community professionals • Teachers

Professionals	external expertise		community professionals for better HIV/AIDS	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • instruction 	
Responsive Training for Teachers based on	To help teachers gain better skills in HIV/AIDS instruction	Conduct training responsive to the demographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct profiling of the teachers • Craft personalized learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School head • Learning Facilitators • Teachers
Demographics	while considering their demographics	profile of teachers Tailor learning activities suited to the preferences and needs of teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • programs to target HIV/AIDS instruction 	

DISCUSSION

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skills

The findings of this study align with recent studies such as *“Teachers’ Knowledge and Communication Practices on HIV/AIDS in Secondary Schools in Kenya”* (Muturi, Kidd & Daniels, 2022), which emphasized limited access to communication resources among educators. Similarly, Kaaya et al. (2023), in their study *“Sociodemographic Variations in Communication on Sexuality and HIV/AIDS Among In-School Adolescents in Tanzania”*, found that while teachers were respectful and open, they struggled to use storytelling and critical thinking strategies effectively—mirroring the moderate scores in those areas.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

These findings of the study are corroborated by recent research studies. For instance, *“Teachers’ Organizational Competence in Delivering HIV/AIDS Education in Nigerian Secondary Schools”* by Okafor & Eze (2022) found that while teachers were confident in lesson planning and sequencing, they struggled with integrating HIV/AIDS topics across subjects and aligning them with national curriculum standards. Similarly, *“Curriculum Integration and Teacher Preparedness in HIV/AIDS Education: A Study in South African Schools”* by Mkhize & Dlamini (2023) emphasized that educators often lacked training in cross-disciplinary approaches and interactive activity design, despite showing moderate competence in using credible sources and assessments.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Classroom Management Skills

The findings are supported by recent research studies. In “Classroom Management Strategies in HIV/AIDS Education: A Study of Secondary School Teachers in Nigeria” (Adebola, 2022), researchers found that while teachers were moderately skilled in maintaining respectful discussions and managing disclosures, they often lacked specialized training to handle emotionally charged or disruptive situations effectively. Similarly, “*Creating Inclusive Learning Environments for HIV/AIDS Education in Philippine Classrooms*” by Bercasio (2023) emphasized the importance of peer collaboration and emotional safety, noting that teachers who actively fostered student cooperation and openness were more successful in reducing stigma and encouraging engagement.

Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

These findings are supported by recent research studies. In “Teacher Adaptability and Inclusive HIV/AIDS Education in Sub-Saharan Africa” (Adebayo & Mthembu, 2022), the authors found that while teachers were moderately competent in adjusting instructional methods, many lacked access to updated resources and interdisciplinary support—echoing the moderate scores in collaboration and integration of new findings. Similarly, “Instructional Flexibility and Student-Centered Approaches in HIV/AIDS Education: A Philippine Perspective” by Santos & Del Rosario (2023) emphasized that educators who adapted their teaching based on student feedback and emotional readiness were more effective in reducing stigma and improving comprehension.

Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

These findings are supported by recent research studies. In “Utilization of Teaching Strategies in HIV/AIDS Education Among Secondary School Teachers in Nigeria” (Okonkwo & Ibrahim, 2022), the authors found that while teachers frequently used interactive and peer-based methods, they rarely incorporated multimedia tools or community-based activities due to limited access and logistical constraints. Similarly, “Innovative Pedagogies for HIV/AIDS Education in Southeast Asia: A Mixed-Methods Study” by Reyes & Tan (2023) emphasized that integration across subjects was highly effective in reinforcing HIV/AIDS content, but the use of expert speakers and outreach programs remained low due to institutional barriers.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers moderately make use of several strategies in HIV/AIDS teaching with specific vigor in interactive, participatory, and integrative modes. These results indicate that although teachers use a robust set of student-centered practices, a stronger focus on multimedia integration, community engagement, and expert partnership might further increase the richness and effectiveness of HIV/AIDS education.

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Communication Skills

The demographic profile age is significantly correlated to the following indicators: comfortably engage in discussing HIV/AIDS-related issues with students ($r = .192^*$, $p < 0.013$), listen attentively to students' questions and concerns regarding HIV/AIDS ($r = .199^{**}$, $p < 0.010$), able to describe HIV/AIDS-related issues without instilling fear or stigma ($r = .155^*$, $p < 0.046$), feel at ease dispelling myths and misconceptions regarding HIV/AIDS in class ($r = .285^{**}$, $p < 0.000$), and able to conduct HIV/AIDS discussions that encourage critical thinking ($r = .157^*$, $p < 0.043$) which means that respondents whose ages are 26-35 years old are more likely to demonstrate strong communication competence in HIV/AIDS education.

However, the indicator employing simple and suitable language when describing HIV/AIDS concepts ($r = -.194^*$, $p < 0.012$) is negatively correlated which implies that they are less inclined to use simple and suitable language when explaining HIV/AIDS concepts. This suggests that educators within the 26–35 age bracket may rely more heavily on technical or academic terminology, potentially limiting the accessibility of their communication for diverse audiences.

Moreover, a significant correlation exists between demographic profile highest educational attainment and indicator feel at ease dispelling myths and misconceptions regarding HIV/AIDS in class ($r = .165^*$, $p < 0.033$) which means that college graduate educators are more likely to feel comfortable addressing and correcting myths and misconceptions about HIV/AIDS during classroom discussions.

As to the demographic profile major field of specialization, the indicator "comfortably engage in discussing HIV/AIDS-related issues with students" ($r = -.181^*$, $p < 0.019$) is negatively correlated, which implies that educators majoring in science and values education are less likely to feel at ease when addressing HIV/AIDS topics in the classroom.

As to years in service, the indicator employs different communication aids (e.g., videos, posters) to support HIV/AIDS education is correlated ($r = -.156^*$, $p < 0.045$) which means that respondents who have 5-15 years in service are less likely to employ varied communication aids such as videos, posters, and other visual tools to support HIV/AIDS education. The negative correlation ($r = -.156^*$, $p < 0.045$) suggests that educators with 5–15 years of service may rely more on traditional teaching methods and less on multimedia or interactive resources.

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Organization Skills

Data revealed that a significant correlation on the demographic profile age with the following indicators: plan structured lesson plans for the instruction of HIV/AIDS content ($r = .212^{**}$, $p < 0.006$), successfully sequence HIV/AIDS lessons for logical information

flow ($r = .273^{**}$, $p < 0.000$), and test students' knowledge of HIV/AIDS through quizzes or tests ($r = .306^{**}$, $p < 0.000$). This suggests that individuals in this age group may be at a stage in their careers where they possess both the enthusiasm of early professional experience and the foundational pedagogical skills gained through recent academic training or ongoing professional development.

Highest educational attainment is significantly correlated to the indicator successfully sequence HIV/AIDS lessons for logical information flow ($r = .317^{**}$, $p < 0.000$) which implies that college graduate educators are more likely to effectively organize HIV/AIDS lessons in a coherent and logical sequence. The strong positive indicates that those who have attained a college degree possess the instructional planning skills necessary to present HIV/AIDS content in a structured and progressive manner.

A significant correlation exists between the demographic profile years in service and the indicator integrate my HIV/AIDS education lessons with curriculum standards ($r = .163^*$, $p < 0.000$) which means that those 5-15 years in teaching are more likely to integrate HIV/AIDS education lessons with established curriculum standards.

Significant correlation is noted between number of trainings and the indicator integrate my HIV/AIDS education lessons with curriculum standards ($r = .228^{**}$, $p < 0.003$), and work with other teachers to incorporate HIV/AIDS education into other subjects ($r = .249^{**}$, $p < 0.003$). This indicates that the number of trainings an educator has attended positively influences their ability to integrate HIV/AIDS education into curriculum standards and collaborate with colleagues across subject areas.

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Classroom Management Skills

Using Pearson r correlation, the demographic profile age is correlated with the following indicators: foster a stigma-free classroom culture when discussing HIV/AIDS ($r = .232^{**}$, $p < 0.003$), employ methods to sustain students' interest and attention when discussing HIV/AIDS ($r = .184^*$, $p < 0.018$), and facilitate peer cooperation in HIV/AIDS learning ($r = .480^{**}$, $p < 0.00$) which indicates that young educators are more likely to demonstrate inclusive, engaging, and collaborative teaching practices when delivering HIV/AIDS education.

Furthermore, a negative correlation was also found out between age and on the indicators provide opportunities for all students to feel secure and at ease sharing thoughts on HIV/AIDS discussions ($r = -.214^{**}$, $p < 0.005$), reinforce positively to facilitate student involvement in HIV/AIDS education ($r = -.302^{**}$, $p < 0.000$), adjust my strategy when students are not comfortable talking about HIV/AIDS ($r = -.237^{**}$, $p < 0.002$). This indicates that as age increases, educators are less likely to exhibit emotionally responsive and student-centered behaviors during HIV/AIDS discussions.

As to highest educational attainment, the following indicators have a significant correlation: provide opportunities for all students to feel secure and at ease sharing thoughts on HIV/AIDS discussions ($r = -.163^*$, $p < 0.035$). adjust my strategy when students are not comfortable talking about HIV/AIDS ($r = -.251^{**}$, $p < 0.001$), and facilitate peer cooperation in HIV/AIDS learning ($r = .282^{**}$, $p < 0.000$) which implies that educators with higher educational attainment show mixed tendencies in their approach to HIV/AIDS education.

As to years in service, the following indicators have a significant correlation: reinforce positively to facilitate student involvement in HIV/AIDS education ($r = .207^*$, $p < 0.007$), and facilitate peer cooperation in HIV/AIDS learning ($r = -.187^*$, $p < 0.016$) which means that educators with 5-15 years in service are more likely to use positive reinforcement to encourage student involvement in HIV/AIDS education, but less likely to promote peer cooperation during HIV/AIDS-related learning activities. *On the other hand, the negative correlation* implies that as teaching experience increases, educators may rely more on individual or teacher- led instruction rather than collaborative, peer-based learning approaches.

As to the number of trainings, the indicators manage disruptive behavior well during HIV/AIDS instruction ($r = .237^*$, $p < 0.002$), and resolve conflicts or disagreements that crop up during HIV/AIDS discussions ($r = .176^*$, $p < 0.023$) has a significant correlation wherein the number of trainings is positively associated with educators' ability to manage classroom dynamics effectively during HIV/AIDS instruction. The significant correlations indicate that as educators attend more trainings, they become better equipped to handle behavioral challenges and navigate sensitive discussions with greater confidence and skill.

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Level of Competence in Teaching HIV/AIDS as to Adaptability

The indicator age is significantly correlated in the indicators such as willing to incorporate new teaching materials and resources for HIV/AIDS ($r = -.196^*$, $p < 0.011$), ready to attend extra training to improve my HIV/AIDS teaching capabilities ($r = .196^*$, $p < 0.011$), and work jointly with school health professionals to enhance HIV/AIDS education ($r = -.153^*$, $p < 0.048$) which implies that younger educators are more open to innovation, collaboration, and professional growth in the context of HIV/AIDS education.

As to highest educational attainment, there is a significant correlation on the indicator adapt communication style according to the maturity level of students ($r = -.165^*$, $p < 0.033$) which implies that educators with higher educational attainment may be less likely to adjust their communication style based on the maturity level of their students.

The demographic profile years in service is significantly correlated to the indicator willing to incorporate new teaching materials and resources for HIV/AIDS ($r = .159^*$, $p < 0.040$) that indicates educators with more years in service are slightly more inclined to incorporate new teaching materials and resources for HIV/AIDS education.

As to the number of trainings, it is significantly correlated on the indicator adapt instructional strategies according to the needs of students in HIV/AIDS instruction ($r = -.189^*$ $p < 0.015$) which means that as the number of trainings increases, educators may be slightly less likely to adapt their instructional strategies based on students' individual needs during HIV/AIDS instruction.

Correlational Analysis between Demographic Profiles to Extent of Utilization of Strategies in Teaching about HIV/AIDS

The age is significantly correlated with the indicators Role-Playing and Scenarios ($r = -.196^*$ $p < 0.011$), Games and Quizzes ($r = .196^*$ $p < 0.011$), and Debates and Critical Thinking Activities ($r = -.153^*$ $p < 0.048$). This implies that younger educators are more inclined to use games and quizzes in HIV/AIDS instruction, while older educators are less likely to employ role-playing, scenarios, and debates or critical thinking activities.

The highest educational attainment shows a significant correlation on the indicator Peer Education and Group Work ($r = -.165^*$ $p < 0.003$) which means that educators with higher educational attainment are slightly less likely to implement peer education and group work strategies in HIV/AIDS instruction. The negative correlation suggests that as academic qualifications increase, there may be a tendency to favor more formal, instructor

The demographic profile years in service is significantly correlated to the indicator Multimedia Integration ($r = .159^*$ $p < 0.040$) which means that educators with more years in service are slightly more likely to integrate multimedia tools into their HIV/AIDS instruction. The positive correlation suggests that as teaching experience increases, so does the tendency to incorporate digital resources such as videos, presentations, interactive modules, and other multimedia formats to enhance lesson delivery.

As to the number of trainings, it was observed that there is a significant correlation on the indicator Interactive Discussions ($r = -.189^*$ $p < 0.015$) which implies that as the number of trainings increases, educators may be slightly less likely to engage in interactive discussions during HIV/AIDS instruction.

Conclusions

1. The respondents are mostly young, moderately experienced, and concentrated in MAPEH. While most hold college degrees, there is room for growth in advanced education and training, highlighting the need for continued professional development.
2. Overall, teachers demonstrate moderate competence in teaching HIV/AIDS—showing strengths in respectful communication, content balance, supportive classroom environments, and adaptability to student maturity—though gaps remain in multimedia use, curriculum integration, classroom management, and collaboration with health professionals.

3. Teachers moderately use various strategies in teaching HIV/AIDS, focusing on interactive methods and subject integration, but limited use of multimedia, guest speakers, and community outreach suggests a need for greater access to external resources and technology to enhance instruction.
4. The respondents' demographic profile—particularly age, educational attainment, years in service, and number of trainings—significantly influences their competence in teaching HIV/AIDS across communication, organization, classroom management, adaptability, and strategy use.
5. The demographic profile of the respondents—specifically age, educational attainment, years in service, and number of trainings—shows a significant relationship with their utilization of strategies in teaching HIV/AIDS.

Recommendations

1. Utilize the proposed action plan to enhance the level of competence and the teaching strategies on HIV/AIDS Education.
2. Provide training focused on flexible, student-centered, and emotionally responsive HIV/AIDS teaching methods.
3. Increase access to multimedia tools, guest speakers, and community outreach opportunities.
4. Offer workshops to help teachers embed HIV/AIDS topics across subjects and align with curriculum standards.
5. Customize professional development based on teachers' age, experience, and education level.
6. Promote teacher collaboration and sharing of best practices in HIV/AIDS instruction.
7. Ensure training promotes adaptable and interactive teaching, not just rigid content delivery.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher strictly complied with the ethical standards in the conduct of this study. Informed consent was properly obtained from all respondents, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from participation at any time without any consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were carefully maintained, and all procedures were carried out in accordance with the Data Privacy Act. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the research process. The author further declares that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. All findings were interpreted objectively, without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes. Additionally, the author discloses that Artificial Intelligence (AI) was utilized only as a tool to assist in writing and editing for clarity, but all ideas, analyses, and interpretations remain the original work of the researcher.

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- **The Researcher**

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